

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842
ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

MULTIDISCIPLINARY E-PUBLICATION

Vol. IV Issue VII, July 2024

Monthly Issue

International Circulation

Pinagpala
PUBLISHING SERVICES

NBDB Reg. No. 3269

DTI Business Reg. No. 3034433

TIN 293-150-678/ Business Permit No. 8183

San Vicente, Tarlac City, Philippines, 2300

pinagpalapublishingservices@gmail.com

+639985799958

*"Write. Connect.
Educate."*

 @pinagpalapublishing

 pinagpala_publishing

 www.pinagpalapublishing.com

World Education Connect

Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue VII (July 2024), p.20 International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

Combating Corruption: The Role of Education and Integrity in Society

Anthony V. Alimonsurin, MAEd

Assistant Professor I

DEBESMSCAT - Cawayan Campus

Region V

Corruption is defined as the misuse of entrusted public power or function for private benefits (Tiana, September 2012). It has detrimental effects on society, impacting the economic domain, quality of governance, and social and political spheres. In the book "Education against Corruption: A Manual for Teachers" (2012), it is suggested that citizens must be given the opportunity to become aware of the effects of corruption on themselves and society as a whole. Education can play a pivotal role in teaching the young to act and think with integrity.

Corruption manifests in many forms, such as bribery and the mismanagement of state-owned property, and it has been widely practiced in every organization, implicitly or explicitly. This behavior has become habitual for many, as if conscience no longer exists, and this act is often mistakenly categorized as acceptable because it appears to benefit everyone involved. Once the mind becomes corrupted, the behavior tends to perpetuate. This behavior is not limited to the highly intellectual and wealthy; it also includes those living below the poverty line.

I have heard rumors, though unconfirmed, about cases of corruption in education. It is perplexing and disheartening to think that teachers, who embody great knowledge and ideal values, could engage in such vulgar acts. Instances of corruption in the education sector include falsifying documents, ghost deliveries of modules or textbooks, creating ghost students, accepting bribes, and abusing power.

How can we combat this when it seems so widespread and accepted? As a simple teacher and individual in society, I strive to uphold honesty and keep my integrity intact. If everyone commits to honesty and integrity, they may be less susceptible to corruption. Secondly, it is crucial to be a voice for truth. While this may be challenging due to fear, if everyone harbors goodness in their hearts and selflessly guides others towards integrity, it can lead to significant positive change.

Corruption must be addressed seriously and eradicated as soon as possible for the betterment of society and to preserve the goodness in human hearts. We must stand against the tide as long as it aligns with the truth.

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.12744290

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.